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Artificial Intelligence And Academic Achievement Of Students In Public Universities In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The investigated the relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State. Three research questions and three null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was eighteen thousand, four hundred and seven (18407) students of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Igbariam. A sample of 400 respondents was selected using purposive sampling technique. Artificial intelligence Scale (AIS) was used for data collection. Students result in one course was used to measure academic achievement. The instruments were face validated by three experts. The reliability of the instruments were determined using Cronbach Alpha coefficient which yielded coefficient values of 0.76 for AIS. Simple regression analysis was used to answer the research questions and test hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of students. The study also found that there is a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of male and female students. The study further found that there is a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of younger (100 to 200 level) and older (300-400) students. The study concluded that there is a significant relationship between artificial intelligence usage and students' academic achievement. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that public universities in Anambra State should formally integrate AI-powered tools and platforms (e.g., intelligent tutoring systems, plagiarism checkers, personalized learning platforms like ChatGPT, Khan Academy, etc.) into the teaching-learning process across all faculties.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Academic Achievement, Students, Public Universities

INTRODUCTION

The importance of students' academic achievement cannot be overemphasized. Academic achievement is an important parameter in measuring success in students. The issue of students' academic achievement is very crucial in the sense that the quality of school, teacher and every other input determines the output which is students' academic achievement. Education has recently been included among the basic needs of individuals. This was why the government of Nigeria in 1999 declared education as basic, free and compulsory for its entire citizen. In addition, individuals and organizations have made concerted effort to ensure that the best is derived as output from the educational system. Academic achievement refers to the height of formal education successfully attained by an individual in the course of pursuing a career. It involves a product of effort or series of effort.

Academic achievement is a test for the measurement and comparison of skills in various fields of academics or study. Stiggings cited in Soliu et al (2017) saw academic achievement as something a learner does or achieves at school, college, or university, in class, in a laboratory or field work. Academic

achievement refers to achievement of individuals' objective to various types of knowledge and skills. The objectives are established based on the age, prior learning and capacity of individuals with regards to education, socialization and qualification.

Academic achievement is what learners are able to accomplish through the execution of class work in the school (Omeh, 2017). Some of the purposes of academic achievement according to Omeh include: to determine the relative effectiveness of a programme in terms of students behaviour output; to identify students growth or lack of growth in acquiring desirable knowledge of their teaching technique and learning material; to help motivate students to learn as they discover their progress or lack of progress in given tasks; to encourage students to develop a sense of discipline and systematic study habits; to acquaint parent or guardians with their children's achievement; to predict the general trend in the development of teaching and learning process; to make reliable decision about education planning and to provide educational administrators with adequate information about teachers effectiveness and school needs.

In recent times, educators in Nigeria have been increasingly concerned about the need to improve on the academic achievement of students (Akubuiro, 2018). In the same vein, Akomolafe (2019) asserted that parents, teachers and society in general are worried and apprehensive about the best way to improve academic standards, achievement and performances. Moreso, Soyinka cited in Essien (2017) observed that the educational system in Nigeria needs

restructuring. He further stated that, academic standard has fallen drastically and the quality of graduates produced is subject to re-examination. Observations and reports have shown that success or high academic achievement has become a Herculean task to accomplish by students in recent times. Students' poor performances in school have continued to pose a serious concern to government agencies, parents and the students themselves (Uoro 2017). Academic achievement is a critical indicator of educational success and is influenced by multiple factors, including teaching quality, learning resources, student motivation, and the learning environment. This has lead government and its agencies to venture into technological innovations to advance teaching and learning. Among these technological innovations, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a powerful tool with the potential to revolutionize teaching and learning processes.

Artificial Intelligence refers to the branch of computer science that focuses on creating machines or software capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence. These tasks include learning, reasoning, problem-solving, understanding language, recognizing patterns, and making decisions (Jayson, 2024). In simpler terms, AI enables computers and systems to mimic cognitive functions such as thinking, learning from experience, and adapting to new information, allowing them to perform complex activities without explicit human programming for every task (Zhang & Lu, 2021). Leslie et al. (2021) explained that AI systems consist of algorithmic models created to perform cognitive or perceptual tasks in the real world, tasks that were once solely the domain of human cognitive processes like thinking, evaluating, and reasoning. In addition, UNICEF (2021) explained that AI is a machine-driven system capable of making forecasts, offering suggestions, or arriving at choices that impact tangible or digital surroundings, based on predetermined human objectives. Artificial intelligence (AI) operates by autonomously acquiring the knowledge to perform tasks. These AI systems engage with us and exert their influence on our surroundings, whether through direct or indirect means. Therefore, AI functions independently and has the ability to adjust their actions by acquiring knowledge about the prevailing circumstances (Ugwoke et al, 2025).

Artificial Intelligence is the simulation of human intelligence in machines that are programmed to think, learn, and perform tasks traditionally requiring human cognition (Klutka et al, 2018). In educational settings, AI applications include intelligent tutoring systems, personalized learning platforms, automated grading, and data-driven insights into student performance. Edionwe (2024) noted that artificial Intelligence was developed as an academic discipline in the 1950s it emerges was found to be a systemic for students' ability to interpret, learn, and achieve specific tasks from data presentation. It refer to analytical, human-inspired intelligence because of the features it contains, together with the exhibited

outputs that involve cognitive, emotional, and social academic display of knowledge (Chatterjee & Bhattacharya, 2020).

Numerous AI tools are in educational practices. Chatbots, chatGPT, virtual tutors, and educational gaming applications offer substantial benefits in fostering self-directed and tailored learning experiences (Zirawaga et al., 2017). AI chatbots and chatGPT are revolutionising the manner in which students gain knowledge. Specifically, Holmes et al. (2022) remarked that chatbots constitute AI systems strategically designed to autonomously interpret natural language and provide responses to inquiries. The chatbots provide instantaneous and personalised guidance to students, addressing their queries and steering them through the learning experiences. The Artificial Intelligent Index Report [AIIR] (2023) asserted that chatGPT is capable of generating text responses akin to human writing, addressing questions, prompts, and even crafting university-level essays. In the same vein, Chen et al (2020) remarked that chatGPT created by OpenAI can generate assessment content, automate processes like test and assignment grading, while also customizing and tailoring assessments based on individual student competencies and inclinations.

Artificial intelligence has the potential to address some of these factors by offering adaptive learning experiences tailored to individual student needs, providing real-time feedback, and facilitating better resource allocation. Understanding the relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement is therefore crucial for policymakers, educators, and stakeholders to optimize AI adoption and improve educational outcomes (Ahmad et al, 2023). Advanced AI technology can be harnessed to enhance teaching and learning processes. With the increasing popularity of mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets, along with advancements in network technology, many educational applications based on generative AI technology have emerged. These applications offer students convenient learning methods, enhancing their understanding and mastery of knowledge (Adiguzel et al, 2023).

Additionally, some applications leverage generative AI to provide realtime, intelligent processes for personalized teaching. These systems can automatically adjust the difficulty and content of courses based on a student's learning performance and level, delivering tailored learning tasks and exercises (Khosravi et al, 2022). Furthermore, these systems can generate relevant learning resources and paths based on a student's habits and needs, promoting more efficient and purposeful learning. They also offer real-time feedback and suggestions to help students correct errors and improve their learning strategies. Moreover, intelligent teaching systems can interact with parents and teachers, providing insights into students' learning progress and performance to enable more comprehensive and effective educational support (Yu et al, 2023). But the effectiveness of artificial intelligence in ensuring higher academic achievement can be affected by demographic factors such as students academic level and gender.

The student's class level is considered as a variable of interest in this study. The students are as new and old students. The newly admitted students are usually found at 100-200 levels while the older ones are found in 300-400 or 50 depending on a person's course of study. The younger students tend to live a more restrictive life and are adjusting to the new environment. Their usage of artificial intelligence tools might be low due to low level of exposure unlike the older students who are very much familiar with the environment and the necessary technological innovation that can enhance learning outcome. To this end, the attitude of young and old students towards the adoption of artificial intelligence may not be the same.

Also, gender is an important variable of interest in this study. Gender is an important variable in the school system. The importance of gender in educational achievement of students cannot be sidelined. Gender refers to the condition of being male or female. Kanno (2018) contended that gender is an analytic concept that describes sociological roles, cultural responsibilities and expectations of men and women in a given society or cultural setting. Oluwaseun et al (2022) explained that gender describes the personality traits, attitudes, behaviours, values, relative power, influence, roles and expectation that society ascribes to the two sexes on a differential basis. Therefore, gender is a psychological term and a cultural construct developed by society to differentiate between the roles, behaviour, mental and emotional attributes of males and females (Lee et al, 2022). Hence, Okeke (2018) described the males' attributes as bold, aggressive, tactful, economical use of words while the females are fearful, timid, gentle, dull, submissive and talkative.

The gender concept seeks to distinguish between the social and historical construction of male and female on the one hand and sex on the other, as well as to explain power relationships between men and women and how they relate in and with society. Gender constitutes a structure of social practice that establishes relations of power, attitudes and hierarchies, not only among people, but also among groups and institutions, which would simply overcome the analysis or individual perception of being female or male (Saleha et al, 2021). This category permits an understanding of socially predefined roles for men and women as perpetrators of unequal hierarchical relations. Gender is the range of physical, biological, mental and behavioural characteristics pertaining to and differentiating between masculinity and femininity. Depending on the context, gender may refer to biological sex (the state of being male or female. Gender issues are currently the main focus of discussion in research all over the world, Nigeria inclusive (Veni & Merlene, 2017). The question of gender is a matter of great concern especially among academics and policy formulators. In our digital age, artificial intelligence is an essential driving force in ensuring effective teaching and learning particularly in tertiary institution. However, there is disparity in the usage of artificial intelligence based on gender. Hence the need to examine how gender and student level influence the relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Higher education institutions have been increasingly adopting contemporary technologies and methods to enhance learning outcomes in a more scalable and affordable manner. Among these advancements, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools, particularly generative AI applications like ChatGPT, has gained significant attention. These AI-driven platforms can generate essays, articles, and other forms of academic content, offering students and educators innovative ways to improve teaching and learning processes. However, the rapid proliferation of such technologies has raised critical concerns, particularly regarding issues like academic integrity, intellectual laziness, and the transparency of AI-generated content. As AI tools continue to reshape educational practices, questions regarding their impact on students' academic achievement and the ethical implications of their use remain largely unexamined. Especially within the context of Nigerian universities

Also, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies in education has rapidly transformed teaching and learning processes worldwide. However, in Nigerian public universities, the extent to which AI tools and applications influence students' academic achievement remains unclear. Despite increasing adoption of AI-driven learning platforms, virtual tutors, and automated assessment systems, there is limited empirical evidence on how these technologies impact students' performance and learning outcomes in the Nigerian context. Moreover, challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited digital literacy, and varying access to AI resources may affect the effectiveness of AI in enhancing academic achievement.

Despite the increasing integration of technology in education, the academic achievement of students at public universities, remains a significant concern. Traditional teaching methods often fail to adequately engage students or address their individual learning needs, leading to suboptimal learning outcomes. Moreover, disparities in academic achievement between male and female students persist, highlighting the need for more inclusive and effective educational strategies. This gap raises important questions about the actual relationship between AI usage and students' academic success, including whether AI contributes positively to learning or if there are barriers that diminish its potential benefits. In Nigeria, public universities are increasingly adopting digital tools and technologies to improve academic delivery and administration. However, the integration of AI in Nigerian higher education is still in its nascent stages, with varied levels of awareness, access, and utilization among students and educators. Despite the promising capabilities of AI to enhance personalized learning experiences and academic support, the extent to which AI influences students' academic achievement in Nigerian public universities remains under-explored. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the relationship between Artificial Intelligence adoption and academic achievement among students in public universities in Anambra State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study.

1. What is the relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of male and female students in public universities in Anambra State?
3. What is the relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of younger (100 to 200 level) and older (300-400) students in public universities in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide this study and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State?
2. There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of male and female students in public universities in Anambra State?
3. There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of younger (100 to 200 level) and older (300-400) students in public universities in Anambra State?

METHOD

The study adopted correlational research design. The design was adopted to investigate the relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State. The study was carried out in Anambra State of Nigeria. The State has two public universities, seven private universities, two colleges of education and two polytechnics. The study concentrated on the state owned university which is Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University. The undergraduates of Faculty of Management Sciences, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam were studied. The population of the study consists of eighteen thousand, four hundred and seven (18407) students of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Igbariam (Office of the Registrar, 2025). The sample for the study was 400 undergraduates, comprising 200 males, 200 females, 267 lower level students and 133 higher levels students selected from the population. Proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to draw the sample for the study. Stratification was based on gender and level of study. Out of the 15 faculties in COOU, Faculty of Management Sciences was selected. Thereafter, 3% of the students in the faculty were sampled. The choice of lower percentage is in line with the opinion of Nwankwo (2010) who maintained that when the population is large, the choice of a lower percentage becomes necessary in order to have a manageable population size.

The instrument for data collection was a researcher developed questionnaire titled Artificial intelligence Scale (AIS). The instrument was structured on a four point rating scale of Strongly Agreed (SA) - 5, Agreed (A) - 4, Undecided (UD) - 3, Disagreed (D) - 2, and Strongly Disagreed (SD) - 1. Academic achievement was measured using the student's scores in one course. Face and content validity of the instruments was established by two experts. Two of the experts are two lecturers in Educational Foundation and one expert from measurement and evaluation, all from the Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University. The instrument for data collection was trial-tested on a representative sample of 30 undergraduates selected from Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka. The institution was chosen for reliability test because they share similar characteristics with COOU, Igbariam. The scores obtained were collated to determine the internal consistency of the items in the instrument. The computation yielded reliability coefficients of 0.76 for AIS. The reliability coefficients was considered high because they fall within the high and very high reliability indices as described by Creswell (2012). The data collected were analyzed thus: simple regression was used to answer the research questions and test hypotheses. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

In this section, the data generated were presented in tables and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. The analyses were done in accordance with the research questions and hypotheses. The first section dealt with the answering of the research questions followed by the testing of hypotheses while the last section covered the summary of findings.

Research Question One: *What is the relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of the Relationship Between Artificial Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Students

	B	SE	β
Constant	18.353	0.441	
Artificial Intelligence	0.792	0.021	0.517
R	0.117		
R ²	0.614		
Adj.R ²	0.513		

Table 1 analyzed the relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State. The Table indicated that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.792 indicating that a unit increase in student usage of artificial intelligence will leads to 0.517 increase in academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State. The coefficient of determination (R²) value of 0.614 showed that 61.4 percent of the variations in academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State are predicted by the variation in students' usage of artificial intelligence. This suggests that artificial intelligence has positive relationship with academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State.

Research Question Two: *What is the relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of male and female students in public universities in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of the Relationship Between Artificial Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Male and Female Students

		B	SE	β
Male	Constant	18.603	0.650	
	Artificial Intelligence	0.460	0.031	0.577
	R	0.077		
	R ²	0.546		
	Adj.R ²	0.514		
Female	Constant	18.373	0.612	
	Artificial Intelligence	0.276	0.329	0.597
	R	0.097		
	R ²	0.569		
	Adj.R ²	0.548		

Table 2 measured the relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of male and female students in public universities in Anambra State. The Table showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) for male students is 0.460 and this indicates that a unit increase in usage of artificial intelligence will likely lead to 0.460 increases in academic achievement of male students. The coefficient of determination (R²) value of 0.546 showed that artificial intelligence is responsible for 54.6 percent of the variations in academic achievement of male students.

Table 2 also showed that the regression coefficient (R) for female students is 0.276 and this indicates that a unit increase in use of artificial intelligence will lead to 0.276 increases in academic achievement of female undergraduates. The coefficient of determination (R²) value of 0.569 indicates that artificial intelligence is responsible for 56.9 percent of the variations in academic achievement of female students. This suggested that the significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement is stronger in male students than female undergraduates in public universities in Anambra.

Research Question Three: *What is the relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of younger (100 to 200 level) and older (300-400) students in public universities in Anambra State?*

Table 3: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of the Relationship Between Artificial Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Younger (100 to 200 level) and Older (300-400) Students

		B	SE	β
Lower Level of Study	Constant	18.420	0.615	
	Artificial Intelligence	0.275	0.029	0.495
	R	0.095		
	R ²	0.619		
	Adj.R ²	0.588		
Higher Level of Study	Constant	18.558	0.649	
	Artificial Intelligence	0.164	0.031	0.580
	R	0.080		
	R ²	0.536		
	Adj.R ²	0.505		

Table 3 measured the relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of younger (100 to 200 level) and older (300-400) students in public universities in Anambra State. The table showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) for students in lower (100 – 200) level of study is 0.275 and this indicated that a unit increase in usage of artificial intelligence has significant relationship with academic achievement of younger (100 to 200 level) students. The coefficient of determination (R²) value of 0.619 showed that usage of artificial intelligence caused 61.9 percent of the variations in academic achievement of younger (100 to 200 level) students in public universities in Anambra State.

The table also showed that the regression coefficient (R) for students in higher (100 – 200) level of study is .164 and this showed that a unit increase in usage of artificial intelligence will lead to 0.164 increases in academic achievement of students in higher (100 – 200) level of study. The coefficient of determination (R²) value of 0.536 indicates that usage of artificial intelligence cause 53.6 percent of the variations in academic achievement of students in higher (100 – 200) level of study. This suggested that the positive relationship between artificial intelligence is stronger in students in higher (100 – 200) level of study than students in lower (100 – 200) level of study in public universities in Anambra.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State

Table 4: Simple Regression Analysis Summary for the Relationship Between Artificial Intelligence and Academic Achievement

		B	SE	β	P-value
Constant		18.353	0.441		0.000
Artificial Intelligence		0.792	0.021	0.517	0.000
R	0.117				
R ²	0.614				
Adj.R ²	0.513				
F	19.057				0.000

Table 4 above indicated that the coefficient of the regression result (R) is 0.792 while the R² is .614. The F-ratio associated with these is 19.057 and the P-value = 0.000. Therefore, since P-value is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance, we reject the stated hypothesis. The study therefore concluded that there is a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of male and female students in public universities in Anambra State.

Table 5: Simple Regression Analysis Summary for the Relationship Between Artificial Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Male and Female Students

		<i>B</i>	SE	β	P-value
Male	Constant	18.603	0.650		0.000
	Artificial Intelligence	0.460	0.031	0.577	0.000
	R	0.077			
	R ²	0.546			
	Adj.R ²	0.514			
	F	53.862			0.000
Female	Constant	18.373	0.612		0.000
	Artificial Intelligence	0.276	0.329	0.597	0.009
	R	0.097			
	R ²	0.569			
	Adj.R ²	0.548			
	F	66.881			0.000

Table 5 indicated that the simple regression coefficient (R) for male and female students is 0.460 and 0.276 respectively while the R² is 0.546 and 0.569 respectively. The F-ratio associated with male and female students is 53.862 and 66.881 respectively while the P-value is 0.000 and 0.000 respectively for male and female students. Since the P-values are less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance, the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is inferred that there is a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of male and female students in public universities in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of younger (100 to 200 level) and older (300-400) students in public universities in Anambra State.

Table 6: Simple Regression Analysis Summary for the Relationship Between Artificial Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Younger and Older Students

		<i>B</i>	SE	β	P-value
Lower Level of Study	Constant	18.420	0.615		0.000
	Artificial Intelligence	0.275	0.029	0.495	0.000
	R	0.095			
	R ²	0.619			
	Adj.R ²	0.588			
	F	16.531			0.011
Higher Level of Study	Constant	18.558	0.649		0.000
	Artificial Intelligence	0.164	0.031	0.580	0.038
	R	0.080			
	R ²	0.536			
	Adj.R ²	0.505			
	F	14.303			0.008

Table 6 indicated that the simple regression coefficient (R) for students in lower (100 – 200) levels of study and higher (300 – 400) levels of study is 0.275 and 0.164 respectively while the R² is 0.619 and 0.588 respectively. The F-ratio associated with male and female students is 16.531 and 14.303 respectively while the P-value is 0.011 and 0.008 respectively for students in lower (100 – 200) levels of study and higher (300 – 400) levels of study. Since the P-values are less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance, the hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, it is inferred that there is a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of younger (100 to 200 level) and older (300-400) students in public universities in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study were discussed in line with the research questions and hypotheses that guided the study. It was carried out under the following sub-headings:

The Relationship Between Artificial Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Students

The findings of the study as shown in Table 1 indicated that artificial intelligence has positive relationship with academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State. The result of the null hypothesis one indicated that there is a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State. This finding suggests that the integration and use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools such as intelligent tutoring systems, AI-powered research tools, adaptive learning platforms, and virtual assistants have a meaningful impact on students' academic performance. The positive relationship implies that as students engage more with AI-based educational technologies, their academic outcomes tend to improve. This result aligns with global trends showing that AI in education can enhance learning efficiency, provide personalized learning experiences, and offer timely feedback, all of which contribute to improved academic performance. It supports constructivist learning theories, which emphasize learner-centered environments where technology adapts to individual student needs. Moreover, it is consistent with existing literature showing that AI enhances critical thinking, content mastery, and independent learning among university students. The result of this study agreed with Okon et al (2024) that AI tools have shown a positive impact on students' academic performance. Similarly, Eneh et al (2024) found that the integration of artificial intelligence in education has a significant positive impact on students' academic performance.

The Relationship Between Artificial Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Male and Female Students

The findings of the study as shown on Table 2 indicated that the positive relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement is stronger in male students than female undergraduates in public universities in Anambra. The result of the corresponding null hypothesis shows that there is a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of male and female students in public universities in Anambra State. The finding supports the idea that, when adequately introduced and supported, AI can be a gender-neutral tool for enhancing educational outcomes. This aligns with more recent studies that suggest gender differences in technology use are narrowing, especially in higher education environments. This agrees with the findings of Ngbarabara and Odibo (2024) that integrating generative AI into teaching significantly enhances students' academic performance and promotes gender-responsive pedagogy.

The Relationship Between Artificial Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Younger (100 to 200 Level) and Older (300-400 Level) Students

The findings of the study as shown on Table 3 indicated that the positive relationship between artificial intelligence is stronger in students in higher (100 – 200) level of study than students in lower (100 – 200) level of study in public universities in Anambra. The result of the related null hypothesis showed that there is a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and academic achievement of younger (100 to 200 level) and older (300-400) students in public universities in Anambra State. This finding implies that AI positively impacts both early-stage (younger) and later-stage (older) undergraduate students in their academic journey. It suggests that students across different levels of academic maturity benefit from AI tools, possibly in ways suited to their unique academic needs. For instance, younger students might rely on AI for foundational learning and tutoring, while older students might use AI for research assistance, advanced problem-solving, or project work. The finding of this study is in consonance with the views of Edionwe (2024) that artificial intelligence influences Business Education postgraduate students academic performance.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the relationship between artificial intelligence (AI) and the academic achievement of students in public universities in Anambra State, with particular attention to gender and academic level. The findings revealed a significant relationship between AI usage and students' academic achievement,

indicating that AI tools contribute positively to learning outcomes. Furthermore, the relationship holds true across both male and female students, as well as between younger (100–200 level) and older (300–400 level) students, suggesting that AI's academic benefits are inclusive and widely accessible.

These findings underscore the growing importance of AI in higher education as a tool for enhancing student learning, engagement, and academic success. The results suggest that institutions should embrace AI integration across all levels and demographics, ensuring equitable access, digital literacy support, and appropriate infrastructure to maximize its benefits. Overall, AI presents a valuable opportunity for transforming education in public universities, fostering academic excellence across diverse student populations.

The findings of this study have several important implications for students, educators, university administrators, policymakers, and educational technology developers. These implications highlight the practical steps that can be taken to harness the benefits of artificial intelligence (AI) in improving academic achievement in public universities in Anambra State and beyond. The significant relationship between AI and academic achievement suggests that education policymakers should consider integrating AI into national and institutional education strategies. Policies should support the development and implementation of AI-driven learning platforms, digital infrastructure, and training programs that promote AI literacy among students and educators.

Also, universities should revise curricula to include AI literacy and digital competency as essential skills. Integrating AI tools into teaching and learning processes can help foster personalized and adaptive learning, improve academic outcomes, and prepare students for a technology-driven world. Lecturers and academic staff should be trained in how to effectively use AI tools for instructional delivery and assessment. Equipping educators with the skills to utilize AI will enhance their teaching methods and help them support students' learning needs more efficiently.

The findings show that both male and female students, as well as students at different academic levels, benefit from AI. This emphasizes the importance of ensuring that all students have equal access to AI tools, regardless of gender, level, or socioeconomic background. Institutions should provide the necessary infrastructure, such as internet access, devices, and software, to minimize digital inequality. Universities should invest in AI technologies that support academic activities, such as intelligent tutoring systems, plagiarism detectors, virtual labs, and research assistance tools. Continuous evaluation of these technologies will help institutions choose tools that align with their students' needs and academic goals.

Students must be encouraged to take responsibility for their learning by actively engaging with AI tools. Orientation programs and digital literacy workshops can help students, especially those in the early stages of their university education, to understand and make effective use of AI in their academic work. The study opens the door for more in-depth research into the specific types of AI tools that most significantly impact academic achievement. It also suggests a need for innovation in locally developed AI solutions that are tailored to the educational context in Nigeria and Sub-Saharan Africa. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Public universities in Anambra State should formally integrate AI-powered tools and platforms (e.g., intelligent tutoring systems, plagiarism checkers, personalized learning platforms like ChatGPT, Khan Academy, etc.) into the teaching-learning process across all faculties.
2. Public universities should design and implement AI literacy and training programs that target both male and female students equally, with attention to encouraging more female participation in AI-related activities.
3. The universities should develop differentiated AI learning support systems for younger (100–200 level) and older (300–400 level) students. For instance, For 100–200 level, they should use AI to support foundational knowledge and study habits; while for 300–400 level, they should use AI for advanced research assistance, project work, and thesis writing support.

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